

Title: Detecting zones and threat on 3D body in security airports using deep learning machine

Name: Abel Ag Rb Guimaraes

Affiliation: The G. Raymond Chang School of Ryerson University, Toronto, ON M5B2K3, Canada

Name: Ghassem Tofighi

Affiliation: Electrical and Computer Engineering Department of Ryerson University, Toronto, ON M5B2K3, Canada

INTRODUCTION:

To be able to accurately identify objects camouflaged in the human body through artificial intelligence is one of the big challenge facing security today. There is, nowadays, a worldwide warning regarding airport security. The Transportation Security Administration (TSA) has deployed 1,800 units Advanced Image Technology (AIT) throughout the airports on USA and the acquisition cost per unit is about \$175,000. To fully implement this system, it cost about 1.17 billion. Adding on it the Department of Homeland Security's (DHS) in USA has a higher false alarm, produced from their algorithms using today's scanners at the airports. Considering this scenario, this paper work will present a model to do the classification of the regions of the body's images using supervised machine learning to identify the threats hired in the bodies. The results will be analyzed to verify the true or false of the information collected in the model.

AIM:

The objectives proposed in this research are: Produce an algorithm that fractionated the human body image in regions to be able to identify the body's region correctly.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The dataset used in this research comes from DHS and Kaggle competition at:

<https://www.kaggle.com/c/passenger-screening-algorithm-challenge/data/> .

From the total of 929 bodies we limited for a sample of 200 bodies to be analyzed; It will produced a total of 287660 sliced images of the bodies. A first approach is to divide the bodies in 17 regions that can contain threat or cannot. To pull the raw images from 3D data files we used a program to slice the body in the z direction, it used 200 bodies from TSA database, in a extension of a3d file. Each scanned sliced view has the length of the body through a z axis coordinate. The file a3d can be worked with the sliced plane (x, y) image of the body, and the aps file was used to locate the threat in the body. To pull the threats, all bodies was rotated to localize the threat and its coordinate. Those coordinates were saved in a table with the extension of csv file. To filter images and produce a binary image, every slice of the body was filter to get the Region of Interest (ROI). It was used a threshold filter that clean the images to produce the segmentation. For normalization it was used a Gaussian convolution. After segmentation and label the regions we divided the body through the z axis in a proportion of 8 heads, then divided again the body in left and right, to get 16 zones, and finally, divided zone 8 and 10 to get the

zone 9, making a total of 17 zones. The figure below shows a 3D assembled sliced zones of a body.

SEGMENTATION

Fig. 1. Final assembled sliced 17 zones labelled of binary images in z coordinates.

To obtain the final image, the raw image was multiplied with the labeled image. This step prepares the final image and save in a template directory to be loaded to a Digits interface. A Multiplication process gets the labeled image and multiply with the raw image to get the real intensity of the image, it focuses on the ROI of the image. After that, all sliced image were saved in directories zones and threat zones. The training data was separated with 60% and the validation and test take the rest of the portion. The trained data was submitted in a configured model called CNN (Y. Lecun 1998), with the solver type Stochastic Gradient Decent (SGD) using the network AlexNet and frame work Tensorflow. The AlexNet (A. Krizhevsky 2012) network consists of 7 layers, 5 convolutions by 5 max-pools and 2 regression layers at the end.

RESULTS:

After the AlexNet process and CNN learning, a function model was produced. This model could classify images in zones. Once the model was trained, we checked the accuracy on unseen test data. This was done using the confusion matrix evaluating the recall and precision of the trained model, comparing the predict class with the actual class. After obtained the metric, was possible

to use the ROC curve to compare the classifier. The results were saved and the curves was plotted. The database created was loaded to produce a total of 287660 images that was submitted to training, validation and test. Analyzing the histograms of images below, we saw that the data is unbalanced, especially with the threats (at the right side of the histograms) .

HISTOGRAM OF THE DATA SET

Fig. 2. Histograms of train, validation and test from the database images.

The training zones were fitted with a total of 172596 images (60%), using splitted images to train; to validation were used splitted images in a total of 57532 (20%) and for test was used 57534 images (20 %) and a format of 256x256 PNG image.

The training, validation and test were performed in an Ubuntu machine that has 16GB of memory, a I7 processor and a Nvidia GPU of 6GB. After 30 epochs, in the Figure 3, the model shows an average accuracy for the validation data of 98.2863% and a loss of 0.091319.

Accuracy and Loss

Fig. 3. Graph of Accuracy and loss with 30 epochs.

This was obtained with a shuffled data using AlexNet with Tensor-flow. The data transformation used a subtract mean image and data augmentation to do the flipping for the threat zones and it produced more balance data, as well, using a contrast of 0.8 factor in the images. We used Digits 1 image to visualize the Statistics. When running this process, it generates plots of weights from

the responses of the network flow input image. The statistical information in every convolution layer parameter includes: frequency, mean and standard deviation. In a well-trained network, smooth filters without noisy patterns are usually discovered. A smooth pattern without noise is an indicator that the training process is sufficiently long, and likely no over-fitting occurred. In addition, visualization of the activation of the network's features is a helpful technique to explore training progress. In deeper layers, the features become sparser and localized, and visualization helps to explore any potential dead filters (Sarraf and Tofghi 2016). The smoothness of the convolution images are demonstrated below Figure 4:

Fig. 4. Statistics of the convolution, activations and weights.

To get a real result, it was used a different test data to enforce the validation of the model. It obtained a Top-1 accuracy of 99.31% and Top-5 accuracy of 100%. A confusion matrix was produced, it shows all the accuracies by class zones, most of them has results upper to 98%. From the confusion matrix we obtained Recall and Precision of the model. Starting with the analyses of Recall and Precision based on the results of Classifying Many Images Test and their Confusion Matrix in Figure 5. Figure 6 shows in more details all Precision and Recall by zones. It can be analyzed more precisely about how much true positives are recovering from the test images, as well as, the precision of this true positives. It can analyze all zones individually and most of them has a 100% in area for both rates.

Confusion Matrix

Confusion matrix																
	zone threat15	zone threat16	zone threat17	zone threat2	zone threat3	zone threat4	zone threat5	zone threat6	zone threat7	zone threat8	zone threat9	Per-class accuracy				
zone threat1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	98.48%				
zone threat2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	99.81%				
zone threat3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	98.7%				
zone threat4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	98.92%				
zone threat5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	98.45%				
zone threat6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	97.15%				
zone threat7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	98.99%				
zone threat8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	98.58%				
zone threat9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	99.92%				
zone threat10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	98.84%				
zone threat11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	97.88%				
zone threat12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	99.1%				
zone threat13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	99.62%				
zone threat14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	99.86%				
zone threat15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	99.78%				
zone threat16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	99.7%				
zone threat17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	99.95%				
zone threat18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	90.53%				
zone threat19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	98.1%				
zone threat20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	98.61%				
zone threat21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	97.48%				
zone threat22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	97.4%				
zone threat23	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	96.07%				
zone threat24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100.0%				

Fig. 5. Confusion Matrix using classify many images summary from Digits.

Results of Recall and Precision

Fig. 6. Recall and Precision average and for every zone.

CONCLUSIONS:

Considering the proposal in the Introduction of this research, this paper work intended to present a model to do the classification of the regions of the body's images using supervised machine learning to identify the threats hired in the bodies. Moreover, produce an algorithm that fractionated the human body image in regions to be able to identify the body's region correctly. In this paper work, it was developed a method to do the segmentation of the body in zones. It was presented 34 zones (considering 17 zones with left and right regions plus the threats zones) to do the learning process. Using robust module CNN with Stochastic Gradient Decent (SGD) and AlexNet, the model could learn the zones with threat or not. Combining with filters, the model could classify those zones of the bodies with a robust result that can help TSA agency security in all airports of North America and world. A big data files was used to train this deep

learning to extract features using convolution neural network that can produce a faster learning provide by Nvidia Digits framework. One important point to be considered here is the fact that the model worked for the trained images of the sample used, it was not considered any external image. Another point is that the result produced was highly accurate for predict zones, it can indicate an overfitting of learning. To prove that, it is necessary to do more test using external bodies, besides that the model need a balance data, that is, more information about the threats. This research showed in average an accuracy of 100% of the bodies zones, as well as, a recall and precision with the same 100% result for the most of zones.

KEYWORDS:

Neural Network; Segmentation; Deep learning; DHS; Security;

BIOGRAPHY:

Abel Ag Rb Guimaraes has a Bsc in Electrical Engineering from FEI University (Faculty of Industrial Engineering) in Sao Paulo, Brazil. He is a Senior Developer Programmer and he has completed his Certificate in Big Data at The G. Raymond Chang School of Ryerson University in Toronto and has a MSc in Robotics Artificial Intelligence (Computer Vision) at FEI University (Faculty of Industrial Engineering) in Sao Paulo, Brazil. He worked for more than 20 years as a Senior Program Developer in larger projects and great companies in Canada, USA and Brazil, for instance IBM, using many programming languages as Java, C++, Python, R, Perl and Matlab.

Ghassem Tofighi has BSc in Electrical Engineering (Communication) from Sharif University of Technology, Tehran, Iran, MSc in Artificial Intelligence from the University of Isfahan, Iran, and Ph.D. in Electrical and Computer Engineering, from Ryerson University, Canada. Ghassem has also worked as a Research Scientist in Silicon Valley, USA, and as a Senior R&D Engineer in Tehran. His research interests are in the areas of Computer Vision, Machine Learning, and Data Science. He has published several scientific papers and patents and worked as instructor for Electrical Engineering, Mathematics, Computer Science, and Business Management courses. He is also CEO of Sina Media Lab which focuses on technology consulting, online learning platforms and developing intelligent mobile application.